

Role of JD-R model in upticking innovative work behaviour among higher education faculty

Abhilasha Dixit and Yogesh Upadhyay

Jiwaji University, Department of Management, Gwalior, India

Received 25 March 2020
Revised 19 August 2020
Accepted 3 January 2021

Abstract

Purpose – In the backdrop of job demands-resources model, the purpose of this paper is to investigate the effect of selected job resources (job autonomy and rewards and recognition) and job demands (problem with work) on innovative work behaviour through the mediation of employee engagement in the higher education sector of India.

Design/methodology/approach – The sample consists of randomly selected 275 teachers from higher education institutions from a city in India. This study used PLS-SEM for data analysis.

Findings – The results suggest that employee engagement associates closely with innovative work behaviour. Job autonomy, one of the resources, affects innovative work behaviour directly and its effect does not move via employee engagement. Further, reward and recognition does not impact innovative work behaviour directly, rather, its effect moves through employee engagement. Finally, the work suggests that employee engagement mediates between selected job resources and job demands and innovative work behaviour.

Research limitations/implications – This study can be extended to include more demands and resources which are unique to academic institutions. For example, a transparent career path to all teachers or a high-octane research culture can serve as a boon. Additionally, their interaction effect can also be studied. The present study being a cross-sectional study, at best, offers a snap-shot view of relationship among the variables.

Practical implications – This study shall help organizations to use job resources and job demands to enhance teachers' engagement and innovative work behaviour. Specifically, results of this study offer a reason to academic institutions to give more autonomy and rewards to their teachers to eke out innovative work behaviour.

Social implications – Firstly, this study will have a positive outcome for students who will be the prime beneficiaries of innovative work behaviour of teachers. Secondly, broadly the society and its constituents will get benefited by improvement in research outcomes.

Originality/value – The outcome of this study proposes that job autonomy and reward and recognition do not connect with employee engagement and innovative work behaviour in a known way.

Keywords Innovative work behaviour, Employee engagement, JD-R model

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

Research contributions suggest innovation as a means to establish and uphold lasting competitive advantage (Drucker, 1985; Kanter, 1988). Innovation is also considered as a

basic element of business success and improved organisational performance (Damanpour, Szabat, & Evan, 1989; Visnjic, Wiengarten, & Neely, 2016). Considering the critical role of innovations, organisations regard employees as a key resource and, therefore, expect their creative contribution in all the areas in which they are serving. Employees' innovativeness in discharging their jobs is broadly known as innovative work behaviour (hereinafter IWB). IWB includes search, generation, promotion and realization of unique ideas in organisational practices (Jong & Hartog, 2010). We lately also observe an attempt to identify factors that promote research, which signifies IWB, at higher education institutions (Fussy, 2018). But such attempts are very few in quantum.

Research plays a primarily role in building reputation of academic institutions. QS World University Ranking gives 40% weightage to academic reputation and 20% weightage to citations (QS World University Rankings – Methodology, 2016). Similarly, Shanghai (*Shanghai Ranking Academic Excellence Survey 2018 Methodology | Shanghai Ranking—2018, 2021*) and Times Ranking (*World University Rankings, 2019*) also give a considerable weightage to research in ranking higher education institutions of the world. The referred criteria clearly vindicate the role of teachers in exhibiting innovative work behaviour at higher education institutions. For example, a study by Bakker, Hakanen, Demerouti and Xanthopoulou (2007) of 805 Finish teachers, using job demands-resources (hence forth JD-R) model (Demerouti, Bakker, Nachreiner, & Schaufeli, 2001; Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), demonstrated that innovativeness also helps them in keeping up with dynamic interactions that take place with the students.

JD-R model explicates as to how two components of work environment, namely, demands and resources, contribute towards workers burnout and engagement (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Innovative work behaviour is an extra-role performance of employees which is an outcome of employee engagement (Reijseger, Peeters, Taris, & Schaufeli, 2017; Kim, Kolb, & Kim, 2013). JD-R model is regarded as context neutral (Taris, Leisink, & Schaufeli, 2017); therefore, it has been used in many domains, including academics. There are a very few instances (Lambriex-Schmitz, van der Klink, Beusaert, Bijker, & Segers, 2020; Messmann, Stoffers, van der Heijden, & Mulder, 2017), where JD-R model has been used to predict IWB among teachers in higher education sector. The present study aims at the identification of drivers of IWB of teachers serving in higher education sector in the backdrop of JD-R model.

Based on the model, and with the help of review of extant literature, we took two resources, i.e. autonomy and reward and recognition, and one demand, i.e. the problem with work, as predictors of employee engagement. Researchers indicate job autonomy and reward and recognition as major predictors of employee engagement (e.g. Janssen, 2000; Saks, 2006). Extending the model, the study also investigates the impact of employee engagement on IWB. Therefore, the major aim of the study is to measure the direct and indirect effect of job resources and job demands on IWB of teachers.

This study is unique in the sense that it is the first, to best of our awareness, to be conducted in the higher education sector in India, towards teachers' IWB using the JD-R model. The role of "problem with work" as job demand, which has been underestimated by the researchers (Janssen, 2000), has been included in the model.

2. Hypotheses development

In JD-R model two processes operate simultaneously. The first one, the energetical process, helps in predicting health problems via burnout and the second one, the motivation process, assists in predicting via engagement in-role and extra-role behaviours of employees (Hakanen, Perhoniemi, & Toppinen-Tanner, 2008). We, in the present study, are using the

motivational route in predicting IWB of teachers in higher education. Review of variables and proposed hypotheses based on extant literature are given below:

2.1 Job demand resource model and employee engagement

The term “engagement” is popularly used to indicate an employee’s involvement, commitment, participation, focussed efforts and state of being geared (Schaufeli, 2012). Kahn’s (1990) theory offers an insight into what leads to personal engagement and disengagement. Traditionally, employee engagement is considered as a “positive-fulfilling, work-related state of mind characterised by vigour, dedication and absorption” (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004, p. 295).

Being engaged is about enjoying the work, even in off hours, and not taking it as a burdened responsibility (Shuck & Wollard, 2010). It is not about being a hard worker or being workaholic. Such employees are full of energy, performers, committed and better organizational citizens (Saks, 2006). Schaufeli and Bakker’s (2004) JD-R model offered a motivational process which argues that job resources contribute towards employee engagement.

JD-R model is an integrative theoretical model that explains what enhances employee engagement and, at the same time, reduces burnout. Every job environment consists of certain job resources and job demands. Demerouti et al. (2001, p. 501) explained job demands as “aspects of the job that require sustained physical or mental effort and are, therefore, associated with certain physiological and psychological costs”. They restrain employees’ performance and reduce energy. On the other hand, job resources are associated with positive psychological and physiological aspects of work offered by an organisation (i.e. job autonomy, rewards, supervisory support and developmental feedback, etc.) that help in achieving goals.

The use of JD-R model is popular in many domains including academics (Han, Yin, Wang, & Zhang, 2020; Messmann et al. 2017). Bakker, Demerouti, & Euwema (2005), in a survey of 1,012 employees of an academic institution, found that job demands and job resources, four each, were predictors of burnout. Bakker and Demerouti (2007), via their study of 805 Finnish teachers, argued that job resources helped in coping with high job demands and boosting engagement. A recent longitudinal study, Dicke et al. (2018) also supported positive association of job resources and teachers’ engagement. Various authors found that the JD-R model also leads to innovative work behaviour of employees (Dediu, Leka, & Jain, 2018; De Spiegelaere, Van Gyes, De Witte, Niesen, & Van Hootegem, 2014).

2.2 Impact of job autonomy on employee engagement and innovative work behaviour of employees

Janssen (2000, p. 288) defines IWB as “the intentional creation, introduction and application of new ideas within a work role, group or organisation, to benefit role performance, the group, or the organisation”. IWB of employees has been linked to positive organisational performance and successful operation in a changing business environment (Hakanen et al. 2008).

Job autonomy has been argued to be a key antecedent in determining IWB based on several theories like job control theory (Karasek, 1979), job characteristics theory (Hackman & Oldham, 1976), job demand resource model (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004) and others. Further, Krishnan et al. (2013) also used social exchange theory to explain IWB by employees. According to them, employees who are given freedom to perform feel indebted and respond with positive work behaviour, i.e. IWB. Role of job autonomy in positively impacting IWB has received a significant attention from researchers (Chiu, Lun, & Bond, 2018; De Spiegelaere et al. 2014). It has shown a positive role in prediction of engagement, affective commitment and job satisfaction of teachers (Brenninkmeijer, Demerouti, Le Blanc, & van Hetty Emmerik, 2010). The effect of job autonomy in positively impacting teachers’ work engagement has also found

support in longitudinal studies (Vera, Salanova, & Lorente, 2012). Therefore, the present enquiry centres around whether a teacher's ownership of tasks serves as a key determinant of IWB (Martin, Salanova, & Peiró, 2007) and employee engagement. Thus, we hypothesize:

H1a. Job autonomy is positively and significantly related to employee engagement.

H1b. Job autonomy is positively and significantly related to IWB of employees.

2.3 Effect of reward and recognition on employee engagement and innovative work behaviour

The contribution of Kahn (1990) and Robinson et al. (2004) is synthesized by Moussa (2013, p. 43) as “employees become engaged in their work if they receive socio-emotional and economic value for their work, when they do not receive what they expect, they tend to withdraw from their roles and disengage themselves”. In the backdrop of social exchange theory, Janssen (2000) defined IWB as a deliberate creation effort with new ideas and suggested that it is facilitated by effort-reward fairness. Ramamoorthy, Flood, Slattery, & Sardessai (2005) exhibited that when employees feel that organisations reward their effort and meet their expectations, they may increase their obligation to engage in the discretionary behaviour, i.e. to innovate. Tarry (1996) suggested that inadequate reward and recognition may not prohibit innovation but may reduce its likelihood (Abramson & Littman, 2002). When work is rewarded and recognised, employees believe in meaningfulness of their work and they stay engaged at work (Chirkowska-Smolak, 2012; Scanlan and Still, 2019). Bhatnagar (2013) found reward and recognition as mediator between perceived supervisory support and innovation. Thus, research considers reward and recognition as an important predictor of employee engagement and innovation. Therefore, we hypothesize:

H2a. Reward and recognition are positively and significantly related to employee engagement.

H2b. Reward and recognition are positively and significantly related to IWB.

2.4 Relationship of the problem with work and employee engagement

One of the assumptions on which JD-R model rests is that every occupation has its set of challenges. These challenges are tagged as job demands (e.g. work pressure, problem with work, emotional pressure). The review suggests that job demands have an inverse relationship with employee engagement (Breevaart, Bakker, Demerouti, & Hetland, 2012; Schaufeli, Bakker, & Van Rhenen, 2009). Though broadly job demands have attained adequate attention of researchers because of their vital role in predicting employee engagement and burnout (Bakker & Demerouti, 2013, 2014; Hakanen et al. 2008) but “problem with work” variable has been left unattended within the ambit of JD-R model. Therefore, we propose:

H3. Problem with work is negatively and significantly related to employee engagement.

2.5 Employee engagement as a mediator of the job demands-resources model and innovative work behaviour

The review of extant research indicates that employee engagement showcases a positive relation with in-role and extra-role performance. Though the research suggests that employee engagement is a predictor of IWB (Chughtai & Buckley, 2011; Kwon & Kim, 2020),

the study by [Agarwal, Datta, Blake-Beard and Bhargava \(2012\)](#) also argued that employee engagement may also plays a role of mediator between IWB and other antecedents. [De Spiegelaere et al. \(2014\)](#) found employee engagement partially mediated between JD-R (job autonomy and insecurity) and IWB. [Wang et al. \(2015\)](#) too found mediation by employee engagement between job insecurity, job autonomy and IWB. Therefore, we propose:

- H4. Employee engagement is positively and significantly related to IWB.
- H5a. Employee engagement mediates the relationship between autonomy and IWB.
- H5b. Employee engagement mediates the relationship between reward and recognition and IWB.
- H5c. Employee engagement mediates the relationship between problem with work and IWB.

Figure 1.
Proposed model
(based on a literature review)

Figure 2.
Final model with path coefficient and R-square (after removing insignificant paths) $p < 0.05$

3. Research methodology

The employee level data was collected with the help of a standardized questionnaire. The sample consisted of teachers of various higher education institutions located in Gwalior, India. The sample of 275 respondents was selected on a random basis from the list of 2500 teachers serving at higher education institutions in Gwalior, India, which comes to around 10.30%. The sample consists of 35% female and 65% of male employees. A total of 49% of employees had a postgraduate degree and the remaining 51% of employees were in possession of a PhD degree.

3.1 Measures

Job autonomy was measured by using the scale by Oldham and Cummings (1996). It consists of two items. The response ranges from very little to very much on a seven-point scale. Reward and recognition was measured by using the scale by Spector (1985) which consists of four items ranging from very little to very much on a seven-point scale. Problem with work was measured by using the scale by Van Veldhove & Meijman (1994) which consists of four items ranging from never to always on five-point scale. Employee engagement was measured with "UWES-Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004), which consist of nine five-point Likert scale items. IWB was assessed with nine item scale proposed by Janssen (2000) and measured on a five-point Likert scale.

3.2 Data analysis

This study uses PLS-SEM (Hair, Risher, Sarstedt, & Ringle, 2019) in predicting key target constructs. PLS-SEM overcomes the limitation of small sample size and offers a higher statistical power. PLS-SEM does not rely on strict data assumptions as compared to CB-SEM (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2011).

At first, we considered outer-path loadings of various constructs and deleted items which were having a value of less than 0.50 (Sarstedt, Ringle, & Hair, 2017). Later, reliability was assessed using Cronbach alpha and composite reliability. Convergent validity was judged with the help of average variance extracted (AVE). Henseler et al. (2016) found better performance of hetrotrait and monotrait ratio (HTMT ratio) for computing discriminant validity compared to other methods (Fornell-Larcker criterion). Therefore, we used HTMT ratio to assess discriminant validity.

The collinearity of the constructs was assessed using variance inflation factor (VIF) and the structural model was assessed using criteria of R^2 (explained variance) and Q^2 (predictive accuracy). The value of R^2 may range from 0 to 1, where higher values suggest a higher explained variance (Hair, Sarstedt, Hopkins, & Kuppelwieser, 2014). Q^2 , which suggests predictive accuracy, is calculated on the hold out data, using blindfolding, *vis-à-vis* the data that was used to calculate R^2 . Later, we applied bootstrapping, to check the direct effect and later, inducted mediating variable to arrive at the indirect effects. Finally, for assessing goodness of fit standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) was used to avoid model misspecification.

4. Results

4.1 Reliability and validity

The outer loading is the absolute contribution of each indicator to the construct. We, based on threshold value of less than 0.50, as indicated by Hair et al. (2019), deleted few items, i.e. 8th item of employee engagement scale, 4th item of problem orientation scale and 9th item of IWB scale. The values in Table 1 suggest internal consistency of the model, as Cronbach

alpha values ranged from 0.62 to 0.87 and composite reliability values ranged from 0.82 to 0.92. Though Cronbach alpha of job autonomy is less than 0.70, based on its composite reliability value, we decided to continue with the variable. The values signify that the measuring instruments were reliable. The validity test measures the fitness of theory of a study. This theory of fitness is tested through discriminant and convergent validity. AVE values reported in Table 1 are above the threshold level (0.50) indicated by Hair et al. (2014). Thus, convergent validity is established. Discriminant validity, assessed using HTMT Ratio (Hair et al. 2014), is reported in Table 2. As the value of HTMT of all the constructs is less than 0.90, it establishes discriminant validity of the variables.

4.2 Structural model

As calculated values of VIF are less than 5, they indicate lack of collinearity in the present case (Hair et al. 2019). In this model, R^2 of employee engagement and IWB is 0.115 and 0.189, respectively. In other words, the model has been able to explain 11.5% variance in employee engagement and 18.9% variance in IWB.

Q^2 was calculated using Stone (1974) and Geisser (1974) method. Table 3 exhibits values of R^2 , adjusted R^2 and Q^2 . and Table 4 exhibits direct effect of paths and their p -value.

Table 1.
Reliability and
validity of
measurement scale

Construct	Items	Convergent validity		Internal consistency reliability	
		AVE >0.50	Cronbach alpha 0.60–0.90	Composite reliability 0.60–0.90	
Job autonomy	2	0.546	0.626	0.827	
Reward and recognition	4	0.734	0.879	0.917	
Problem with work	4	0.708	0.681	0.822	
Employee engagement	9	0.505	0.859	0.890	
Innovative work behaviour	9	0.606	0.861	0.894	

Table 2.
Discriminant
validity: heterotrait–
monotrait ratio
(HTMT)

	IWB	Autonomy	Engagement	Problem with work	Reward and recognition
IWB	–	–	–	–	–
Job autonomy	0.325	–	–	–	–
Employee engagement	0.439	0.284	–	–	–
Problem with work	0.110	0.178	0.293	–	–
Reward and recognition	0.232	0.581	0.276	0.268	–

Table 3.
Explained variance
(R^2) and predictive
relevance (Q^2)

	R square	R square adjusted	Q square
IWB	0.189	0.180	0.091
Employee engagement	0.115	0.106	0.049

4.3 Employee engagement as a mediator

We tested mediation by employee engagement using bootstrapping procedure. Bootstrapping results are exhibited in Table 5 indicating specific indirect effects of latent variables on the outcome.

4.4 Fitting the model in Smart-PLS

SRMR as a goodness of fit matrix helps to avoid model misspecification (Henseler et al., 2016). Fit value of less than 0.08 is considered to be an acceptable fit (Henseler et al. 2016; Hu and Bentler, 1999). In this study, SRMR stands to be 0.068. Therefore, the measurement and structural model criterion has an acceptable fit.

The results support that autonomy shows a significant association with IWB (H1a) rather than employee engagement (H1b). The results suggest that reward and recognition were significantly related to employee engagement (H2a), whereas they were insignificant to IWB (H2b). Further, problem with work was found to be negatively related to employee engagement (H3). Also, employee engagement was positively and significantly related to IWB (H4). The findings reveal significant mediation by employee engagement between two resources of JD-R model (reward and recognition, problem with work) and IWB (H5b) and (H5c). However, employee engagement did not mediate between job autonomy and IWB (H5a). Also, the results suggest that out of all the three variables that were part of the model, only job autonomy directly affected IWB. Thus, except H1(a), H2(b) and H5(a), all other hypotheses found support in the study.

5. Discussion

Innovation plays a major role in sustaining competitive advantage for an organization. IWB by teachers is also one of the key sources of innovation that every organization acknowledges and wishes to tap. The present study used JD-R model to study its effectiveness in explaining IWB of teachers. This study was conducted in the higher education sector of India, which remains one of the unexplored areas as far as application of

Hypotheses	Direct effect	t-value	p-value	Result
H1(a) Job Autonomy→Employee Engagement	0.130	1.834	0.067	Not supported
H1(b) Job Autonomy→ IWB	0.207	4.176	0.000	Supported
H2(a) Reward and recognition→ Employee Engagement	0.214	2.267	0.024	Supported
H2(b) Reward and recognition→ IWB	0.117	1.770	0.077	Not supported
H3 Problemwithwork→Employee Engagement	-0.190	3.737	0.000	Supported
H4 Employee Engagement→ IWB	0.336	6.520	0.000	Supported

Table 4.
Total effect, t-values
and p-value

Hypotheses	Specific indirect effects	t-value	p-value	Results
H5(a) Autonomy → Employee Engagement → IWB	0.045	1.615	0.107	Not supported
H5(b) Reward and Recognition→Employee Engagement→ IWB	0.053	2.219	0.027	Supported
H5(c) Problem with work → Employee engagement→ IWB	-0.062	2.725	0.007	Supported

Table 5.
Mediation analysis

JD-R model to explore the same is concerned. We regressed employee engagement on two job resources, i.e. reward and recognition and job autonomy and one job demand, i.e. problem with work. Further, we also hypothesised that employee engagement shall positively affect IWB of teachers. In nutshell, the present study investigated relationship between job resources (reward and recognition, autonomy) and job demands (i.e. the problem with work) and IWB, mediated by employee engagement among teachers in higher education sector.

The present study makes three important contributions. Firstly, job demands, especially problem with work, which did not gain adequate attention of the researchers in the area of employee engagement was included among variables that affect IWB. Secondly, JD-R model-based studies primarily include only job resources in their models. The present work accommodates both job resources as well as job demands into a single model to offer a holistic picture. Thirdly, the present study is about teachers serving at higher education sector of India, which, to our best of the information, is the first such attempt. Additionally, the present work challenges the earlier research outcomes where job autonomy is considered as precursor to employee engagement (Nahrgang, Morgeson, & Hofmann, 2011). Rather, this study argues that job autonomy in-fact is an antecedent to IWB of employees.

There are several key findings of the present work. Firstly, reward and recognition affects teachers' engagement in the hypothesised way, i.e. positively. The outcome is in line with AbuKhalifeh and Som (2013) and Tuan Choo, Mat and Al-Omari (2013) who found reward and recognition as the third highest predictor of employee engagement. Also, it aligns with Maslach and Leiter (2008) and AbuKhalifeh and Som (2013) who proposed reward and recognition as an important area of work-life affecting employee engagement. Secondly, the results suggest that "problem with work", a job demand, affects employee engagement negatively. Though there are mixed results concerning relationship between job demands and engagement (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2007), in general, job demands exhibit negative association with employee engagement (Nahrgang et al. 2011). Though there are very few studies available on problem with work and its effect on engagement, it reconciles with the studies that argue work-related problems negatively connect to engagement (Maslach & Leiter 2008).

Thirdly, the results suggest that the job autonomy does affect employee engagement positively, but the same is statistically insignificant. On the contrary, its effect on IWB is positive and significant. The result of the study is in consonance with De Spiegelaere et al. (2014) who confirmed job autonomy relates to IWB but not with employee engagement. Finally, the results show that employee engagement mediates the relationship between reward and recognition, problem with work and IWB. This result is in line with Janssen (2000) and Scanlan and Still (2019) who suggested that fair reward and recognition evoke positive psychology and further an individual's IWB.

6. Implications

The present study can be extended by including variables such as organisational climate, learning goal orientation and emotional intelligence (Chin et al. 2012; Chughtai & Buckley, 2011) to capture wide spectrum of JD-R model. Additionally, the model can further include job crafting with the help of which employees may make changes in their job demands and job resources (Schuler, Binnewies, & Bürkner, 2019). Additionally, future researcher may also focus on other work-related demands, i.e. emotional and mental demands, along with problem with work.

This study has several managerial implications concerning its findings. Firstly, job demand (problem with work) was found to be negatively related to employee engagement.

This suggests that teachers experiencing problems with work will not stay engaged. Hence organisations need to resolve teachers' problem with work at the earliest to keep them engaged. Otherwise, both students' satisfaction and research output, are expected to suffer. Further, job autonomy was found to be contributing positively to IWB but its relationship with employee engagement was insignificant, though positive. Translating these results for teachers simply means that a teacher may not be dedicated but can still contribute towards quality research courtesy to job autonomy. Therefore, academic institutions that wish to remain at the top or reach to the top, ought to provide job autonomy to their teachers. Positive relationship of reward and recognition and IWB via teachers' engagement suggests the importance to monetary and non-monetary incentives that shall enable them to stay engaged and which in turn shall help them to perform innovatively. Thus, academic institutions who wish to stay competitive and do better, need to provide resources to their teachers and help them to contain problems at work.

Despite these contributions and implications, our study is not without limitations and certain caveats need to be exercised while interpreting the results. Firstly, it is a survey-based study and, therefore, should not be used to infer causal relations among variables. Secondly, our results may partly have self-reported error and influenced by a common method variance. Future studies can overcome self-reported error by seeking supervisor's ratings for assessing innovativeness (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, & Podsakoff, 2012).

References

- AbuKhalifeh, A. N., & Som, A. P. M. (2013). The antecedents affecting employee engagement and organizational performance. *Asian Social Science*, 9(7), 41. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n7p41>
- Agarwal, U. A., Datta, S., Blake-Beard, S., & Bhargava, S. (2012). Linking LMX, innovativework behaviour and turnover intentions: The mediating role of work engagement. *Career Development International*, 17(3), 208–230. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620431211241063>
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2007). The job demands-resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309–328. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940710733115>
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2014). Job demands-resources theory. In Cooper, C.L. (Ed.), *Wellbeing: a complete reference guide. Work and wellbeing*, (pp. 1–28). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118539415.wbwell019>
- Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Euwema, M. C. (2005). Job resources buffer the impact of job demands on burnout. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 10(2), 170–180. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/1076-8998.10.2.170>
- Bakker, A. B., Hakanen, J. J., Demerouti, E., & Xanthopoulou, D. (2007). Job resources boost work engagement, particularly when job demands are high. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 99(2), 274–284. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.99.2.274>
- Bhatnagar, J. (2013). Mediator analysis in the management of innovation in Indian knowledge workers: The role of perceived supervisor support, psychological contract, reward and recognition and turnover intention. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25(10), 1395–1416. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2013.870312>
- Brenninkmeijer, V., Demerouti, E., Le Blanc, P. M., & van Hetty Emmerik, I. J. (2010). Regulatory focus at work. *Career Development International*, 15(7), 708–728. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620431011094096>
- Breevaart, K., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Hetland, J. (2012). The measurement of state work engagement: A multilevel factor analytic study. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 28(4), 305–312. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759/a000111>

- Chin, S. T. S., Raman, K., Yeow, J. A., & Eze, U. C. (2012). Relationship between emotional intelligence and spiritual intelligence in nurturing creativity and innovation among successful entrepreneurs: A conceptual framework. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 57, 261–267. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.1184>
- Chirkowska-Smolak, T. (2012). Does work engagement burn out? The person-job fit and levels of burnout and engagement in work. *Polish Psychological Bulletin*, 43(2), 76–85. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10059-012-0009-2>
- Chiu, W. C.-K., Lun, V. M.-C., & Bond, M. H. (2018). Engaging in creative work: The influences of personal value, autonomy at work, and national socialization for self-directedness in 50 nations. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 49(2), 239–260. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022116651336>
- Chughtai, A. A., & Buckley, F. (2011). Work engagement: Antecedents, the mediating role of learning goal orientation and job performance. *Career Development International*, 16(7), 684–705. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620431111187290>
- Damanpour, F., Szabat, K. A., & Evan, W. M. (1989). The relationship between types of innovation and organizational performance. *Journal of Management Studies*, 26(6), 587–602. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.1989.tb00746.x>
- De Spiegelaere, S., Van Gyes, G., De Witte, H., Niesen, W., & Van Hootegem, G. (2014). On the relation of job insecurity, job autonomy, innovative work behaviour and the mediating effect of work engagement: Job insecurity, job autonomy and innovative work behaviour. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 23(3), 318–330. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/caim.12079>
- Dediu, V., Leka, S., & Jain, A. (2018). Job demands, job resources and innovative work behaviour: A European union study. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 27(3), 310–323. Retrieved from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1359432X.2018.1444604>
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499–512. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.86.3.499>
- Dicke, T., Stebner, F., Linninger, C., Kunter, M., & Leutner, D. (2018). A longitudinal study of teachers' occupational well-being: Applying the job demands-resources model. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 23(2), 262–277. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000070>
- Drucker, P. F. (1985). *Innovation and entrepreneurship*, Harper & Row, Publishers, Inc.
- Fussy, D. S. (2018). Policy directions for promoting university research in Tanzania. *Studies in Higher Education*, 43(9), 1573–1585. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2016.1266611>.
- Hackman, J. R., & Oldham, G. R. (1976). Motivation through the design of work: Test of a theory. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, 16(2), 250–279. Retrieved from: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(76\)90016-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(76)90016-7)
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2011). PLS-SEM: Indeed a silver bullet. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), 139–152. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.2753/MTP1069-6679190202>
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2–24. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- Hair, J. F., Jr, Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, V. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106–121. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128>
- Hakanen, J. J., Perhoniemi, R., & Toppinen-Tanner, S. (2008). Positive gain spirals at work: From job resources to work engagement, personal initiative and work-unit innovativeness. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 73(1), 78–91. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2008.01.003>

- Han, J., Yin, H., Wang, J., & Zhang, J. (2020). Job demands and resources as antecedents of university teachers' exhaustion, engagement and job satisfaction. *Educational Psychology, 40*(3), 318–335. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2019.1674249>
- Henseler, J., Hubona, G., & Ray, P. A. (2016). Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: Updated guidelines. *Industrial Management & Data Systems, 116*(1), 2–20. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-09-2015-0382>
- Hu, L., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal, 6*(1), 1–55. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>
- Janssen, O. (2000). Job demands, perceptions of effort-reward fairness and innovative work behaviour. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology, 73*(3), 287–302. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317900167038>
- Janssen, O. (2003). Innovative behaviour and job involvement at the price of conflict and less satisfactory relations with co-workers. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology, 76*(3), 347–364. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1348/096317903769647210>
- Jong, J. D., & Hartog, D. D. (2010). Measuring innovative work behaviour. *Creativity and Innovation Management, 19*(1), 23–36. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.14678691.2010.00547.x>
- Kanter, R. M. (1988). Three tiers for innovation research. *Communication Research, 15*(5), 509–523. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/009365088015005001>
- Karasek, R. A. (1979). Job demands, job decision latitude, and mental strain: Implications for job redesign. *Administrative Science Quarterly, 24*(2), 285–308. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2392498>
- Kim, W., Kolb, J. A., & Kim, T. (2013). The relationship between work engagement and performance: A review of empirical literature and a proposed research agenda. *Human Resource Development Review, 12*(3), 248–276. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484312461635>.
- Krause, D. E. (2004). Influence-based leadership as a determinant of the inclination to innovate and of innovation-related behaviors. *The Leadership Quarterly, 15*(1), 79–102. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2003.12.006>
- Krishnan, R., Ismail, I. R., Samuel, R., & Kanchymalay, K. (2013). The mediating role of work engagement in the relationship between job autonomy and citizenship performance. *World Journal of Social Sciences, 3*(3), 120–131.
- Kwon, K., & Kim, T. (2020). An integrative literature review of employee engagement and innovative behaviour: Revisiting the JD-R model. *Human Resource Management Review, 30*(2), 1–18. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2019.100704>
- Lambriex-Schmitz, P., van der Klink, M. R., Beusaert, S., Bijker, M., & Segers, M. (2020). When innovation in education works: Stimulating teachers' innovative work behaviour. *International Journal of Training and Development, 24*(2), 118–134. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijtd.12175>
- Martin, P., Salanova, M., & Peiró, J. M. (2007). Job demands, job resources and individual innovation at work: Going beyond Karasek's model? *Psicothema, 19*(4), 621–626.
- Mauno, S., Kinnunen, U., & Ruokolainen, M. (2007). Job demands and resources as antecedents of work engagement: A longitudinal study. *Journal of Vocational Behavior, 70*(1), 149–171. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2006.09.002>
- Messmann, G., & Mulder, R. H. (2011). Innovative work behaviour in vocational colleges: Understanding how and why innovations are developed. *Vocations and Learning, 4*(1), 63–84. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-010-9049-y>
- Messmann, G., Stoffers, J., van der Heijden, B., & Mulder, R. H. (2017). Joint effects of job demands and job resources on vocational teachers' innovative work behaviour. *Personnel Review, 46*(8), 1948–1961. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-03-2016-0053>

- Moussa, M. N. (2013). Investigating the high turnover of Saudi nationals versus non-nationals in private sector companies using selected antecedents and consequences of employee engagement. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(18), 41 p. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v8n18p41>
- Nahrgang, J. D., Morgeson, F. P., & Hofmann, D. A. (2011). Safety at work: A meta-analytic investigation of the link between job demands, job resources, burnout, engagement, and safety outcomes. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96(1), 71–94. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0021484>
- Oldham, G. R., & Cummings, A. (1996). Employee creativity: Personal and contextual factors at work. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 39(3), 607–634.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2012). Sources of method bias in social science research and recommendations on how to control it. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 63(1), 539–569. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-120710-100452>.
- Ramamoorthy, N., Flood, P. C., Slattery, T., & Sardesai, R. (2005). Determinants of innovative work behaviour: Development and test of an integrated model. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 14(2), 142–150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8691.2005.00334.x>
- Reijseger, G., Peeters, M. C., Taris, T. W., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2017). From motivation to activation: Why engaged workers are better performers. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 32(2), 117–130. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-016-9435-z>
- Saks, A. M. (2006). Antecedents and consequences of employee engagement. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 21(7), 600–619. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940610690169>
- Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Hair, J. F. (2017). Partial least squares structural equation modeling. C. Homburg, M. Klarmann, & A. Vomberg, (Eds.), *Handbook of market research*, pp. 1–40. Springer International Publishing. in Retrieved from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3319-05542-8_15-1
- Scanlan, J. N., & Still, M. (2019). Relationships between burnout, turnover intention, job satisfaction, job demands and job resources for mental health personnel in an Australian mental health service. *BMC Health Services Research*, 19(1), 1–11. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3841-z>
- Schaufeli, W. B. (2012). Work engagement. What do we know and where do we go? *Romanian Journal of Applied Psychology*, 14(1), 3–10.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement: A multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(3), 293–315. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.248>
- Schaufeli, W. B., Bakker, A. B., & Van Rhenen, W. (2009). How changes in job demands and resources predict burnout, work engagement, and sickness absenteeism. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 30(7), 893–917. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.595>
- Schuler, B. A., Binnewies, C., & Bürkner, P. (2019). The relationship between job crafting, work engagement, and performance: A meta-analysis. *PsyArXiv*, Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/xpf2v>
- Methodology| Shanghai Ranking – 2018. (2021). Retrieved from www.shanghairanking.com/subject-survey/survey-methodology-2020.html#4 (accessed 15 August 2022).Shanghai Ranking Academic Excellence Survey 2018
- Shuck, B., & Wollard, K. (2010). Employee engagement and HRD: A seminal review of the foundations. *Human Resource Development Review*, 9(1), 89–110. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1534484309353560>
- Spector, P. E. (1985). Measurement of human service staff satisfaction: Development of the job satisfaction survey. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 13(6), 693–713. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00929796>
- Suan Choo, L., Mat, N., & Al-Omari, M. (2013). Organizational practices and employee engagement: A case of Malaysia electronics manufacturing firms. *Business Strategy Series*, 14(1), 3–10. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/17515631311295659>

-
- Taris, T. W., Leisink, P. L. M., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2017). Applying occupational health theories to educator stress: Contribution of the job Demands-Resources model. nT. M. McIntyre, S. E. McIntyre, & D. J. Francis, (Eds.), *Educator stress*, pp. 237–259. Springer International Publishing. Retrieved from: https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53053-6_11
- Timms, C., & Brough, P. (2013). “I like being a teacher”: Career satisfaction, the work environment and work engagement. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 51(6), 768–789. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEA-06-2012-0072>
- Van Veldhoven, M., & Meijman, T. F. (1994). *The measurement of psycho-social job demands with a questionnaire: The questionnaire on the experience and evaluation of work (QEEW)*, Dutch Institute for Working Conditions.
- Vera, M., Salanova, M., & Lorente, L. (2012). The predicting role of self-efficacy in the job demands-resources model: A longitudinal study. *Estudios De Psicología*, 33(2), 167–178. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1174/021093912800676439>
- Visnjic, I., Wiengarten, F., & Neely, A. (2016). Only the brave: Product innovation, service business model innovation, and their impact on performance. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 33(1), 36–52. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpim.12254>
- Wang, H., Lu, C., & Siu, O. (2015). Job insecurity and job performance: The moderating role of organizational justice and the mediating role of work engagement. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 100(4), 1249–1258. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038330>
- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2007). The role of personal resources in the job demands-resources model. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 14(2), 121–141. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1037/1072-5245.14.2.121>
- World University Rankings. (2019). Times higher education (the). Retrieved from www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/2020/world-ranking

Corresponding author

Abhilasha Dixit can be contacted at: abhilashaanu@gmail.com

Associate Editor: Germano Glufke Reis

For instructions on how to order reprints of this article, please visit our website:

www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/licensing/reprints.htm

Or contact us for further details: permissions@emeraldinsight.com